

CRITERIA AND INDICATORS FOR EVALUATING THE DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN THE CONTEXT OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. In this article, conceptual approaches to private and social norms of return of funds invested in human capital are scientifically and theoretically covered. At the same time, the evaluation criteria of the UN human development index are indicated and the indicators of human development index of Uzbekistan are analyzed.

Key words: human capital, human development index, human capital assessment, education level improvement, development program, investment in human capital.

One of the most important aspects of economic growth in modern conditions is human capital. The availability of human capital and its effective use determines the country's economy position in the world. In this regard, the formation of the concept of human capital development is appropriate.

The formation and development of the concept of human capital implies a quantitative assessment with extensive use of economic-mathematical and statistical methods. The study of the main methodological approaches to the assessment of human capital made it possible to determine the following systematization:

1. Measurement of human capital using natural indicators;
2. Measurement of human capital based on the assessment of the past period;
3. Measurement of human capital reserve based on return assessment;
4. World Bank approach.¹

It should be noted that the difference in methodological approaches to the measurement of human capital depends on the level of its consideration. Assessment of individual human capital, sector, region or organizations human capital involves the application of a fundamentally different methodological approach. As a result of this research, it is appropriate to describe the territorial aspect in order to achieve future results in the process of making management decisions.

Most economists classify investments in human capital into three types:

¹ Соболева И.В. Парадоксы измерения человеческого капитала: Научный доклад. / И.В. Соболева // М.: Институт экономики РАН, 2009. 50 с. Парушина Н.В. Методы измерения и оценки человеческого капитала (научный обзор) / Н.В. Парушина, Н.А. Лытнева Е.А. Семиделихин // Научное обозрение. Экономические науки, 2017. №2. С. 89-99.

- expenditure on education, including general and special, formal and informal and on-the-job training;
- health care expenses, including expenses for disease prevention, medical services, dietary nutrition, improvement of home conditions;
- moving expenses.

However, the complexity of using this method is that the work is carried out from a statistical point of view, which is unattainable in terms of quantity and quality.

Based on the evaluation of the return of funds invested in human capital, first of all, it is necessary to measure the stock of human capital. At the same time, there are several shortcomings in the calculation of this method:

1. Human capital and physical capital are not comparable when evaluating capital measures.
2. The obtained results cannot be used for calculations at the national and regional level.

An increase in educational attainment affects both earnings and employment. In other words, the potential of people with higher education will be more capitalized than those with basic professional education. In practice, the value method of evaluating the return on the use of human capital (in its many variants) is limited to taking into account only the monetary return. That is why its real reserve is underestimated.

At the same time, private and social standards of return of funds invested in human capital differ in this regard. The first evaluates the efficiency of investments from the point of view of individual investors, and the second from the point of view of society as a whole.

There are two main approaches to calculating the rate of return on human capital. The first approach takes into account the difference between the incomes of people at different levels of education, that is, the "premium of education" and the costs associated with education and the lost profits from economic activity during education.

Within the framework of the second approach, the "production function of income" is considered, which describes the dependence of human income on the level of education, work experience, length of working hours and other factors. Area is a rate-of-return calculation for assessing human capital and is informative, but assessment tools must be flexible for research purposes and account for opportunity costs, which seem almost impossible given individual and regional stratification.

The World Bank approach. According to the definition given by the World Bank, human capital is the ability of people to participate in the production process, their knowledge, experience, and work skills. Investments in human capital are funds spent on health, education, technical training, and activities that allow people to increase their labor productivity.

The World Bank proposes to use the discount method of evaluating human capital through its value. For this, the value of natural and physical capital is subtracted from the value of the total national wealth, and as a result, it becomes the value of human capital, which makes up at least half of the national wealth in most countries.

According to the definition of the United Nations Development Program: "Human development is the process of providing people with a wider range of choices. It is of fundamental importance that such a choice is infinite and changes over time. However, at all levels of development, the ability to use the resources necessary to live a long and healthy life, acquire knowledge and lead a decent life is the main essence of human development. If a person does not have such a basic choice, he cannot use other opportunities"².

The human development index is currently the most widely used criterion for evaluating human capital. It has many advantages, including:

- availability and uniformity of the necessary data (indicators needed to calculate the index are available in almost all countries and are checked centrally by UN components);
- as a result, the possibility of calculating the Human Development Index for a wide range of countries (today there are more than 180 of them);
- the index truly reflects aspects of life that are important for human capital development.

There are also a number of disadvantages of the human development index, including:

- 1) "average income per capita" sub-index (Income Index) does not reflect the real income of the population, as it does not take into account the coefficient of income redistribution. In addition, the average income is already indirectly taken into account in the remaining 2 indicators. In fact, a person cannot spend 10 or even 20 years of his life on education if he does not have enough income to live on. Therefore, life expectancy at present depends largely on the health system, which in turn depends on public and private financing. In other words, there is a "double

² United Nations Development Program (UNDP)". www.un.org.my.Entsiklopediya site:ewikiuz.top

counting" of the monetary factor, which gives economically developed countries a clear advantage in the assessment of human capital;

2) the index takes into account the quantitative and not the qualitative characteristics of human capital. In addition, a number of researchers point out that the data used in the indices provides the annual cross-section of the total human capital as a shortcoming of the indices, while not taking into account the "reserved" share. It does not take into account the share of human capital involved, that is, the capital owned by the economically active population and the processes affecting its change are not considered (only the indicator is determined, but the influencing factors are not taken into account). Therefore, T. Lee, J. Gibson and L. Oxley emphasize that an important element of measuring human capital for the purpose of perspective is to approach it as a flow rather than a stock.

Figure 1. Parameters of UN Human Development Index³

The measurement of human capital of regions and countries is often based on an index approach. National (country) aspects of evaluation are being actively implemented by international organizations:⁴

1. United Nations - Human Development Index⁵

³ Information from the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation "Analysis of Human Development Index - 2020 Report, Actions and Priorities to Achieve KPI" Tashkent 2021.

⁴ "Human Development Report 2020" (PDF). United Nations Development Programme. Pages 22-25. December 9, 2020. Encyclopedia site: ewikiuz.top

⁵ Human development indices and indicators. Statistical Update 2020. [Electronic resource] Access: http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/2020_human_development_statistical_update.pdf.

2. World Bank - Human Capital Index⁶

World Economic Forum in cooperation with Harvard University and Mercer Human Resource Consulting - Human Capital Development Index international consulting company.⁷

Since 1990, the United Nations has been publishing annual Human Development Index reports as part of the United Nations Development Program. The Human Development Index is a comprehensive indicator for assessing the life expectancy, literacy, education and standard of living of the population (Figure 1). It is used to distinguish between countries and to assess the impact of economic policies on the quality of life.⁸

According to the results of the review of the state of human development in 2020, Uzbekistan took the 106th place and was included in the group of developing countries. The dynamics of the Human Development Index of the Republic of Uzbekistan presented in Figure 2 can be described as positive. By 2020, the value of the human development index reached 0.720, and its components had the following values:

- life expectancy at birth – 71.7 years;
- expected study period – 12.1 years;
- average length of study is 11.8 years;
- gross national income per capita - 7142 dollars⁹.

⁶ Human capital development project, World Bank, 2020. [Elektronnyy resurs] Access mode: <http://www.vsemirnyjbank.org/ru/publication/human-capital>.

⁷ The Global Human Capital Report 2020. World Economic Forum. [Electronic resource] The mode is available at: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Global_Human_Capital_Report_2020.pdf.

⁸ United Nations Handbook on Human Capital Measurement, 2016. 138 p. [Electronic resource] Access mode: https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/stats/publications/2016/ECECESSTAT20166_R.pdf

⁹ 2021 reports of the United Nations Development Program on human development in the countries of the world, <http://hdr.undp.org/en/global-reports>

Figure 2. Dynamics of human development index of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹⁰

In 2020, the World Bank implemented the "Human Capital Development" project, which produced an index taking into account the contribution of children's education and health to future labor productivity (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Components of human capital index¹¹ (World Bank methodology)

The productivity of adults who are fully educated and in good health is ideal. This indicator is assigned 1 point, and as a result, index indicators are determined as part of it. The labor productivity of a person born in 2020 in our country is 73.0% of the maximum level that can be achieved by the age of 18, with full education and full health.

Figure 4. Human capital indicators calculated according to the methodology of the United Nations in selected countries, grouped by income level in 2020¹²

¹⁰ <http://hdr.undp.org/en/global-reports>

¹¹ Source: Human capital development project by the author, World Bank, 2020.-Access mode: <http://www.vsemirnyjbank.org/ru/publication/human-capital>.

¹² Income level is defined as gross national product per capita.

In cross-country comparison, Singapore, which has shown economic growth in recent decades, is significantly lower than Japan and South Korea, because this country's policy in the field of education and science is high (Figure 4). The results of the World Bank research revealed a direct relationship between the country's income level and the indicators of the human capital index. According to the developers, this indicator can be used to determine the share of income that countries do not receive due to a lack of human capital.

Its version of the human capital index was presented by the World Economic Forum in its Global Human Capital Report 2017. The index was calculated for 130 countries by different age groups based on the four indicators presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Components of Human Capital Index¹³ (World Economic Forum Methodology)

There are also such initiatives in internal practice. Thus, as part of the implementation of the national index of development of the digital economy based on experience, the assessment of human capital is presented as one of the main factors of the development and use of digital technologies. The goal of the project is to provide the necessary information and analytical support for the management of digital transformation processes at the national, regional and network levels, and to create the necessary tools for this.

Currently, the development of the digital economy in the world is taking place at a rapid pace. The development of the digital economy makes it possible to fully satisfy consumer demand and increase labor productivity in economic sectors and sectors. E-commerce makes it possible to prevent crises on the basis of accelerating the sale of goods and services.¹⁴

It is noted that human capital is becoming the most important factor of digital transformation and economic growth. In this regard, an integrated approach to

¹³ Source: The Global Human Capital Report 2017. World Economic Forum. – The regime is available at: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Global_Human_Capital_Report_2017.pdf.

¹⁴ Nasimov D.A. Improving the methodology of introducing modern forms of employment in the context of the development of the digital economy. / Doctor of Economics (DsC) dissertation. - Tashkent, 2020. p. 174.

its assessment is proposed, which includes three approaches: human capital available in the country; the extent and quality of the system of increasing human capital; the country's ability to retain, attract and utilize talented and skilled personnel.

The reforms and positive changes in all fields carried out in our country in recent years, including the improvement of the population's standard of living, the progress achieved through the fundamental reform of public education and health care systems, not only improve our position in international rankings, but also show that we continue to develop in all directions in the interests of the people.

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